

MY WAY TO THE FUTURE BY LEARNING LANGUAGES AND TRAVELING AROUND THE WORLD TO ENLARGE MY OUTLOOKS

Artikmashrapov Shaxboz Muslim o'g'li

6th grade pupil of public school № 14, Uchkurgan, Namangan

Turaboyeva Gulnora

English teacher at public school № 14, Uchkurgan, Namangan

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Annotation: The author, a 12-year-old boy from Uzbekistan, shares his passion for learning languages and exploring the world. He believes that language learning is crucial for personal growth and cultural understanding, and it can also open up opportunities for his future career. He talks about the benefits of language learning and his current language studies, as well as his dream of becoming a world traveler. He emphasizes the importance of experiencing different cultures and connecting with people from different backgrounds.

Key words: Uzbekistan, language learning, personal growth, cultural understanding, career opportunities, benefits, English, Russian, Uzbek, Korean, French, Chinese, traveling, immersion, cognitive benefits, world traveler.

Аннотация: Автор, 12-летний мальчик из Узбекистана, делится своей страстью к изучению языков и познанию мира. Он считает, что изучение языка имеет решающее значение для личного роста и понимания культур, а также может открыть возможности для его будущей карьеры. Он рассказывает о преимуществах изучения языка и своих текущих исследованиях, а также о своей мечте стать путешественником. Он подчеркивает важность знакомства с разными культурами и общения с людьми из разных слоев общества.

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, изучение языка, личностный рост, культурное понимание, карьерные возможности, преимущества, английский, русский, узбекский, корейский, французский, китайский, путешествия, погружение, познавательные преимущества, путешественник по миру.

I have always been passionate about learning languages and exploring the world. I believe that learning languages is not only important for my future career but also for personal growth and cultural understanding. My dream is to become a world traveler and explore different countries and cultures.

I come from a multicultural and multilingual country, which has over 100 different ethnic groups, each with their own language and culture. Growing up in such a diverse environment has taught me the importance of embracing different cultures and learning new languages. I have always been fascinated by the way language can connect people from different backgrounds, and I believe that by learning different languages, I will be able to communicate with locals, make friends, and experience their culture firsthand.

Learning languages has numerous benefits, both personal and cognitive. It improves memory, problem-solving skills, and creativity. It also enhances critical thinking and decision-making abilities, which are essential skills in any career path. Moreover, learning languages opens up opportunities for personal growth and cultural understanding.

Currently, I am learning English, Russian, and Uzbek. English is an important language to learn since it is widely spoken around the world and is the language of international communication. Russian is another important language in Uzbekistan since it is the second most widely spoken language after Uzbek. Learning Uzbek is also important since it is my native language and has a rich cultural heritage.

In the future, I hope to learn more languages such as Korean, French, and Chinese. Korean is widely spoken in South America and Europe, while French is spoken in many countries in Africa and Europe. Chinese is also an important language to learn since it is spoken by over a billion people in China and other parts of the world.

Traveling around the world is not only a way to enlarge my horizons but also an opportunity to practice my language skills. By traveling to different countries, I will be able to immerse myself in the language and culture, practice my speaking skills, and learn new vocabulary. I believe that traveling is an important part of language learning since it allows you to experience the language in its natural context.

My dream is to become a world traveler and explore different countries and cultures. I want to visit different countries, learn about their culture, and connect with people from different backgrounds. I believe that by doing so, I will be able to gain a deeper understanding of the world and its people.

In addition, I would like to mention about that I am proud to come from a nation of great scholars and linguists. My ancestors were known for their vast knowledge and expertise in many different languages, including Arabic, Persian, Turkish, and Uzbek. Some of the most famous scholars from Uzbekistan include Iskhakhan Ibrat, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Beruni, and many others.

Growing up, I was always fascinated by the stories of my ancestors and their incredible achievements. They were not only masters of language and literature, but they also made significant contributions to fields such as medicine, astronomy, and mathematics. Their legacy lives on today, and I am inspired to follow in their footsteps.

One of the most remarkable things about my ancestors was their ability to communicate with people from different cultures and backgrounds. They understood the importance of language as a tool for building bridges between communities and promoting understanding. This is a lesson that I have taken to heart, and I am currently studying several different languages myself.

Learning languages has opened up a whole new world for me. I am able to connect with people from different countries and cultures, and I have gained a deeper appreciation for the diversity of our world. I believe that language learning is essential for personal growth and cultural understanding, and it can also lead to exciting career opportunities.

As I continue my studies, I am proud to carry on the legacy of my ancestors. I hope to one day become a scholar myself and make my own contributions to the world of language and literature. But more than anything, I dream of traveling the world and experiencing different cultures firsthand. I know that my ancestors would be proud to see me following in their footsteps and carrying on their legacy of knowledge and understanding.

In conclusion, as a young boy from Uzbekistan, I strongly believe that learning languages and traveling around the world is the key to achieving my future dreams. It will not only open up opportunities for me but also allow me to connect with different cultures and gain cognitive benefits. Therefore, I am committed to continuing my language studies and exploring the world.

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